

Structural Fire Response of Polymer Composites

Plate-scale testing

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Motivation: How did I get into this business?

Buckling of laminate

Presentation Overview

- Framework for analysis of failure of composites subjected to combined fire and mechanical loading
- Micromechanics of failure
 - Compression controlled failures
 - Tension controlled failures
- Laminate-level response
- New measurement techniques
- Integration with numerical tools
- Ongoing applications
- Conclusions
- Acknowledgements

Framework for Analysis

Viscoelastic Characterization: E-glass/Vinyl Ester

[±45]_{2s} Laminate
Vetrotex 324/Derakane 510A-40

Creep and recovery data (30° to 170°C & 0.05 to 4 ksi) modeled using Zapas/Crissman visco-plastic model describing creep response to a wide range of temperature & loads

Observations of High Temperature Compression Failures

Vetrotex 324/Derakane 510A-40

Compression Mechanics

Use Budiansky & Fleck compression strength model, assuming a Ramberg-Osgood shear stress-strain relation

$$\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_y} = \frac{\tau}{\tau_y} + \left(\frac{3}{7}\right) \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_y}\right)^n$$

Compression strength modified as a function of temperature and time

$$X_c(T, t) = G(T, t) \left[1 + n(T) \left(\frac{3}{7}\right)^{\frac{1}{n(T)}} \left(\frac{\bar{\phi}}{\gamma_y(T)(n(T)-1)} \right)^{\frac{n(T)-1}{n(T)}} \right]^{-1}$$

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Isothermal Compression Creep Rupture

Shift factors from shear creep compliance used to collapse compression creep rupture data

$$X_C(\xi) = \frac{G_{12}(\xi)}{1 + n \left(\frac{3}{7}\right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \left(\frac{\bar{\phi}}{\gamma_Y}\right)^{\frac{n-1}{n}}}$$

$n = 5.3 \quad (T \approx 30^\circ\text{C})$
 $\gamma_Y = 0.59\% \quad (T \approx 30^\circ\text{C})$
 $\bar{\phi} \approx 10^\circ$

Warp $[0^\circ]_{10}$ and Weft $[90^\circ]_{10}$ coupons of Vetrotex 324/Derakane 510A - 40

Key Conclusion: Temperature-dependent compression strength and time-dependent compression creep rupture are both manifestations of the same viscoelastic behavior of composite

Temperature Effects on E-Glass Tensile Strength

Not only applies to fire, but also thermal recycling

Temperature Effects on E-Glass Tensile Strength

No exposure

450°C exposure

Temperature Effects on E-Glass Tensile Strength

Are Flaws Growing or is Bulk Toughness Decreasing?

Fracture surface of glass fiber containing straight FIB milled notch (239.5 nm deep)

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Sustained Compression Load & One-sided Heat Flux Exposure

(a)

(b)

Sustained Compression Load & One-sided Heat Flux Exposure

$$(EI)_{eq} \frac{d^2\theta(x)}{dx^2} + P\theta(x) = (M_{x,\theta}^T + Pe_0) \left(\frac{8-8K}{L^2} x - \frac{4-4K}{L} \right)$$

Simple Mechanics Model to Predict the Response

Sustained Compression Load & One-sided Heat Flux Exposure

Simple Mechanics Model to Predict the Response

Coupled Viscoelastic, Thermomechanical Model

- Combine partial differential equations representing
 - Viscoelastic mechanical constitutive equation, using rule of mixtures for char and virgin material
 - Decomposition reaction equation (solid mass)
 - Heat transfer equation (temperature)
 - Gas diffusion equation (gas pressure)
- Solve using finite element method in Abaqus
 - Constitutive behavior in UMAT
 - Heat transfer and decomposition in UMATHT1
 - Gas diffusion in UMATHT2 (with pressure, rather than temperature as the variable)
 - Overlay elements used: UMAT and UMATHT1 applied to first layer; UMATHT2 applied to second layer
 - State variables and common blocks

Validation: Experimental Data from RMIT

Temperature

Axial Stress in Fiber Direction

Comparison of the predicted and experimental failure times (compression controlled failure)

Measurement Improvement: TDIC

- Heat flux of 10kW/m^2 (minimal decomposition of front skin)
- No insulation of specimens on back surface to allow for field measurements.
- DIC average on back face recorded for each test.
- Non-uniform heat flux observed due to different densities of balsa
- Delamination of front skin 'cools' back face.

Thermoplastic Battery Enclosures for Electric Vehicles

Lithium-Ion Batteries in Electric Vehicles (EVs)

EVs have attracted substantial interest due to greater efficiency and potential reduced emissions of CO₂.

Challenge: Limited lithium-ion battery capacity

- Larger number of lithium-ion batteries
 - Increase in weight
 - Risk of fire and explosion

Solution?

Replace metallic battery packs with **intumescent thermoplastic polymer-based** composite systems

- Reduced weight
- Improved fire protection
- Lower thermal conductivity

Metal-intensive Battery Pack

Volkswagen. (2019). Key components for a new era – the battery system.

RESEARCH PLAN

Selected Materials

Flame-retardant polypropylene (FR-PP) composites with 30% glass fiber-reinforcement **with controlled characteristics**

- Fiber length
- Flame retardancy

Injection-molded with random fiber length & orientation distribution

Material Characterization

- Thermogravimetric Analysis; TGA
- Thickness expansion
- Thermal Conductivity
- Specific Heat
- Dynamic Mechanical Analysis; DMA

Cp (J/(g*K))

7
6
5
4
3
2

Area: 29.96 J/g

Plate Responses to Fire & Mechanical Loads

- Custom Set-up
- Inverse Heat Transfer; IHT
- IR Temperature Measurements
- DIC Deformations
- Thermocouple Measurements

Validation

- Unexposed Temperature
- Deflection

Simulations

IHT or Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS) for Thermal Loading

Abaqus for Coupled Thermomechanical Modeling

- Thickness expansion via Effective Thermal Conductivity
- Viscoelasticity via Prony Series & User TRS Subroutine
- Thermomechanical Contact Simulation

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

OVERALL GOAL: To predict the coupled thermomechanical behavior of thermoplastic composites for newly manufactured battery pack systems.

Joel, M. EV Battery Types - A Simple Guide. How Does an Electric Vehicle Battery Work? 2024

Lithium-ion battery on top of each plastic module exerts an approximately total gravity weight of 1.1 kN/m^2

External fire or thermal runaway convective and radiative heat source

Plate-scale testing

SAND-BURNER EXPOSURE

Mechanical Loading & Fire

Weight of battery enclosure ≈ 90 N uniformly distributed over the area of the plate.

Initial tests: Four equal 22.5 N and 50 mm diameter steel cylinders weights.

TDIC Measurements of Temperature and Displacement

TDIC Measurements

Out-of-Plane Displacement

Temperature

THERMOMECHANICAL MODELING

Loaded Plates

Subjected to one-sided external fire and various mechanical loading scenarios

4 × 50 mm diameter weights

4 × 100 mm diameter weights

1 × 75 mm diameter weights

Conclusions

- Developed a framework for analysis of failure of composites subjected to combined fire and mechanical loading
- Examined micromechanics of failure using combination of experiments and analysis
 - Shift factors indicate that viscoelasticity controls compression failure (same shift factors for shear creep compliance and compression creep rupture data)
 - Good success in using Budiansky-Fleck type compression model to predict failures
 - Fiber tensile strength changes with temperature in E-glass fibers linked to surface flaw growth
- Relatively simple laminate-level mechanics models can explain key features of laminate out-of-plane deformation during simulated fires
- Integration of material models with numerical tools allows use to predict the failure of E-glass/vinyl ester laminates in a wide range of configurations and size scales
- New measurement techniques such as TDIC have promise in leading to greater understanding of the underlying behavior and validation of modeling tools
- Currently applying to long and short fiber thermoplastic composites for electric vehicle applications

Questions?

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